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SWARMING, ABSCONDING, MIGRATION AND RELATED
PHENOMENA IN UNMANAGED HONEYBEES *APIS MELLIFERA*

*Sciarmatura, fuga, migrazione e fenomeni correlati in colonie di api
non gestite Apis mellifera*

At the end of last century, I discovered that mysterious behavior of nest abandonment by honey bee swarms can be explained based on the universal theory of adaptation and stress, formulated by Hans Selye in the years 1946–1976. Having regard to the fact that the vast majority of the reasons described as causes of nest abandoning by honey bees swarms, e.g. old queen, too small nest, sudden loss of forage etc., have the character of stress stimuli. This point of view was enriched with physiological findings presented by EVEN *et al.* (2012) that confirm that bees can suffer from stress in the form of Selye's General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS).

Additionally, based on the fact that bees can learn and remember that determines the psychological dimension of animal behavior (MACKINTOSH, 1974), I realized that also inability of expression by bees of their inborn instinctive behaviors e.g. feeding larvae etc. may also put them in stress. It especially occurs when their queen is old, sick or the whole colony is in stress which suppresses e.g. social trophallaxis. This can also be result of learning of aversive association connected with “adverse circumstances and experiences” observed by von FRISCH (1965) In general, the level of excitation of CNS in insects according to Nicolaas TINBERGEN (1951), determines the expression of related instinctive behaviour. Such a behaviour according to Konrad LORENZ (1972) is usually automatically triggered in response to so-called key stimuli.

Moreover, analyzing DARWIN's work (1872) in which he described the external expression of emotions in humans and animals, the work of

PANKSEPP (1998), who drew attention to advanced level of sensorimotor consciousness in bees and the work of VANCATA (1995), who found a relationship between the expression of given swarming behaviour and the value of frequency of sound emitted by the colony, I concluded that stress-induced emotional agitation of bees (LIPIŃSKI, 2001, 2006). lies at the root of the expression of swarming behaviors (LIPIŃSKI, 2001).

Significantly the excess of this stimulation drained from the CUN of bees by the tremor of muscles of their thorax and abdomen, as it happens in other animal species and man known as stereotypy, "indicates that the individual has some difficulty in coping with the condition, so it is an indicator of poor welfare" (BROOM & JOHNSTON, 2020). I also concluded that this phenomenon, by causing the combs vibration and/or sounds release due to the movement of the wings, as a key component of set of "dances" continuously sensitize bees for expression of subsequent behaviors incl. final escape from the nest. In this context, the already well-known fact of cognitive expression of instincts in bees, fully proven by Prof. Menzel and his school, allowed me to formulate the thesis that the behavior of nest abandoning by swarms of bees, due to the stressful nature of the stimuli causing it, has all the features of a typical adaptive phenomenon. Bearing in mind that:

1. The queen maintains psychical and reproductive dominance over honeybee colony mainly through calming effect of her own pheromones and partly through the pheromones of the young brood and young worker bees.
2. Any weakness in this calming dominance is expressed in increased sensitivity of especially young bees to unfavorable environmental stimuli which is the main cause of social stress and swarming mood.
3. Swarming mood lies at the base of expression of migratory instinct which is in the root cause of nest abandonment by swarm of honeybees.
4. Intensity of swarming mood, modulated to a large extent by the level of queen substance and larval substance and other nest stimuli, depends mainly on the pressure of stress stimuli and the physiological state of the bees.
5. Swarming mood as a reflex of swarming stress may develop independently from queen cell cycle and vice versa.
6. Construction of swarming queen cells is a symptom of threshold insufficiency of queen substance in the honeybee colony
7. The main "goal" of breeding a new queen is to re-establish the proper level of queen substance in a honeybee colony
8. To most potent stress stimuli (stressors) include: A – insufficiency of queen and larval substance; B – lack of food (nectar, pollen) and

water; C – overcrowding, overheating, disturbance: strange sounds, excitatory fragrances, vibrations etc.

9. Aggregation of bees in clusters, especially in swarm cluster, is an adaptive and defensive behaviour.
10. Recruitment dance into the new nest or forage and other dances are forms of adaptive stereotypy.
11. The sensitivity of bees to stress is strongly genetically determined
12. The psycho-physiological nature of swarming, absconding and migration is similar both in terms of adaptive essence and stress mechanism.

To summarize, nest abandonment is an adaptive response of honey bees in order to cope with the stress caused by unfavourable conditions both inside and outside the hive. A single or multiple dis-joining of the colony is an act of classic swarming under the slow increase of sub-acute pressure of stress stimuli. Whereas rapid increase of acute pressure of these stimuli leads to absconding of the colony, while slow increase of acute pressure leads to its migration.

Moreover, there is no fundamental psycho-physiological difference in adaptive essence of nest abandonment by swarms of honeybees, either in the swarming process of nest abandonment by honey bee swarms (SPNA) as well as similar absconding (APNA) and migration (MPNA) process, with all other intermediate forms of these phenomena (escape of small wedding swarms, etc.). However, each of three processes of nest abandonment (PNA) differs in the course of stress reaction.

In above context, the so-called ‘fission of the colony’ (SEELEY, 1995) which is in progress at the moment of nest abandonment by a swarm in the process of classic swarming, is essentially a secondary phenomenon, enhanced as a result of a group response to a state of culmination of swarm mood by the most stress sensitive (at a given moment) bees (creating a swarm) and not in pre-intended (aimed) act of ‘reproduction’ of a honeybee colony by dividing. So classic swarming can be treated as the reproduction of a honeybee colony only from a mathematical, not biological, point of view. Thus, classic swarming is not reproduction or reproduction of honeybee colonies by division.

Swarming is a biological spontaneous act of the adaptive dis-joining of a honeybee colony under the slow increase of sub-acute pressure of stress stimuli. This phenomenon occurs in the case of natural single or multiple swarming, whereas a fast increase of acute pressure of these stimuli leads to absconding of the colony, while a slow increase of acute pressure leads to its migration.

The essence of the current incorrect interpretation of phenomenon of

classic swarming is a result of the unintentional connection of the term ‘division of bee colony’ with the apparently incorrect notion of ‘reproduction of a bee colony’ as a result of which the false concept that “swarming is a form of reproduction at the colony level, as opposed to the reproduction of individual bees within” (CHUNG & GARY, 1999) arises or that in the life cycle of the honeybee colony is “reproduced by swarming and colony fission in the spring” (KRYGER & MORITZ, 1997; WINSTON, 1991).

At the base of this reasoning lies the unintentional analogy to the reproduction of most animal species which causes a swarm of bees to be associated with the par excellence ‘fetus’. The mentioned double difficulties in understanding the phenomenon of group nest abandonment by bees also deepens the historically-shaped semantic similarity between the terms ‘swarming’ and ‘swarm’.

This causes every swarm of bees leaving the nest to be unintentionally associated with classic swarming in situations when nest abandonment can also be the result of absconding and migration of whole bee colonies. Both of the notions quoted above and terminological inexactness reside deeply in the earlier mentioned hypothesis of Aristotle (who overestimated the role of queens in the process of swarming) and still seems to efficiently block progress in the understanding of both the essence and mechanism of nest abandonment by honeybees – not only in the process of swarming but also in other forms of this phenomenon in situations when similarity of causes leads to: classic swarming, migration and absconding and also clearly indicates that all of them have one mutual adaptive stress nature.

General remark – Considering the complexity of above described psychobiological phenomena, the author encourages readers to consult the book entitled “Essence and mechanism of nest abandonment by honey bee swarms”, especially if they wish to understand the control measures of swarming and related phenomena.

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